

Scientific article

Balancing Actuation Penalties and Wake Recovery: The Efficacy of the Helix in Turbulent Inflows

Authors: Tim Dammann, Wei Yu, Jan-Willem van Wingerden

Published on: Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Volume 3224, Proceedings of TORQUE 2026, Bruges (3–5 June 2026)

Abstract: *The Helix approach mitigates wake losses by employing periodic dynamic individual pitch control to force the wake into a helical structure, thereby accelerating wake recovery through increased ambient mixing. While proven in idealized flows, its operational viability under realistic atmospheric turbulence remains under-characterized. This study isolates the impact of ambient Turbulence Intensity (TI) on Helix efficacy using high-fidelity Large Eddy Simulations (LES) of the IEA-22MW reference turbine. We evaluate the net energy balance by weighing downstream aerodynamic gains against upstream actuation losses across varying TI levels (2.0%–13.1%) and pitch amplitudes (1°–5°). Contrary to the hypothesis that high turbulence negates forced mixing, the strategy proves robust, maintaining net array power gains across all tested conditions without a restrictive “break-even” threshold. In low-turbulence regimes ($I_a = 2.0\%$), peak net gains reach $\sim 18\%$ at optimal actuation ($St \approx 0.28$). In high-turbulence regimes ($I_a = 13.1\%$), gains persist at 2–4%, though the location of peak energy recovery shifts upstream from $x/D \approx 3.5$ to $x/D \approx 2.5$. We confirm that efficacy relies on exciting specific wake instability modes ($St \approx 0.28$) rather than untargeted mixing, establishing the Helix as operationally viable even in turbulent offshore environments.*

Link to article: <https://iopscience.iop.org/volume/1742-6596/3224>

SUDOCO is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement 101122256). Views and opinions expressed herein are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.